

Data Management Plan

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About the PAPILLONS project

PAPILLONS (Plastics in Agricultural Production: Impacts, Lifecycles and LONG-term Sustainability) aims to fill critical knowledge gaps on the sources, behaviour, and long-term ecological and socioeconomic impacts of micro- and nanoplastic (MNP) derived from agricultural plastics (AP) in European soils and provide the scientific background to enable policy, agricultural, and industrial innovation towards sustainable farm production systems. Funded by the European Commission (EC) under the framework of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) programme, PAPILLONS represents a consortium of 20 partners from 12 countries. It is a transdisciplinary cutting-edge research program and brings together Europe's leading experts on MNPs in agricultural soils.

More information about the project can be found at: www.papillons-h2020.eu

About this Deliverable

This report corresponds to the final Data Management Plan – i.e. deliverable D5.4 and encompasses a comprehensive overview of the data collected and/or generated by the PAPILLONS Consortium partners to assess impacts of micro-scale plastics on soil properties, fauna and plants.

The main objective is to fill knowledge gaps on the sources, behaviour, and long-term ecological and socioeconomic impacts of MNPs from AP in European soils and provide the scientific background to enable policy, agricultural and industrial innovation towards sustainable farm production systems. Through novel data collection, generation and analysis PAPILLONS will build a Knowledge Hub to fill these gaps using co-development, sharing and exploitation of AP and MNPs data.

For the final Data Management Plan, PAPILLONS Consortium decided to use Argos - an open-source tool developed by OpenAIRE fully aligned with the OPEN and FAIR principles.

This report describes the 32 datasets produced throughout the PAPILLONS project implementation. For direct access to archived datasets please also check the [PAPILLONS community on Zenodo](#).

List of abbreviations

AP	Agricultural plastic
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
H2020	Horizon 2020
KB	Kilobyte
MB	Megabyte
MNP	Micro- and nanoplastic
MP	Microplastic
NP	Nanoplastic
PAPILLONS	Plastic in Agricultural Production: Impact, Lifecycles and LONG-term Sustainability

1. Subtask 1.1.1. – Chemical composition of main agricultural articles used for protected cultivation systems

Task: Analysis of polymeric composition and chemical additives

This dataset reports the detailed analysis of the possible chemical additives present in the formulations of the agricultural plastics selected in the frame of Task 1.1. The output of this activity consists in the development of a database of the polymer formulations representative of the AP, including type of additives. Identification of additives has been carried out through the ‘suspected target’ approach following a priority list elaborated in collaboration with other partners and stakeholders (Task 1.1.1).

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value) reporting commercial name of analysed products, name of chemical constituents (both polymer and identified chemical additives), CAS number of identified chemical constituents, quantitative or semi-quantitative estimation of amounts of chemical constituted per mass of the bulk product.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

1.1. Data Summary

1.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- To share information

1.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- Sample or specimen data
- Experimental (e.g.
- Gene sequencing data)

Primary data regarding the characterisation of chemical composition and physical properties of agricultural plastics are collected, generated, and shared.

1.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files
- Numerical
- Software

.txt and .xls files of chromatography and mass spectrometry datasets relative to the chemical characterization of agricultural plastics.

1.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

1.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MG (megabyte)

1.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

1.2. Reused Data

1.2.1. Are you reusing the described data and how?

No

1.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

No

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

No

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

No

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Data are stored under .zip file format, or as tabular data (.txt, .csv, .xls type files).

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/10963721>

Please describe if data require proprietary tools to access the data.

Data are included in a .rar folder, to be open with software suites including WinZip, WinRAR, etc.

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

1.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

<https://zenodo.org/records/10963721>

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/records/10963721>

Zenodo

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

Some files will require proprietary software to access, such as MS Office suite for .xls files. Data are included in a .rar folder, to be open with software suites including WinZip, WinRAR, etc.

Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

After publication

1.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

1.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

Describe the data quality assurance processes.

Periodical calibration of the equipment, standardized procedure for sample preparation and analysis, replicated testing.

Will you provide any support for data reuse?

No

1.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

No

Contact persons identified will be responsible for the management of the data.

Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a. Sabrina Carola Carroccio (orcid:0000-0002-9645-0369)

Contact person

b. Pierfrancesco Cerruti (orcid:0000-0003-0822-2866)

Contact person

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Institutional archive

<https://zenodo.org>

1.4. Data security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time.

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

1.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

1.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

2. SubTask 1.1.2. – Physical and technical characterization of main agricultural plastics articles used for protected cultivation systems

Task: Assessment of functionalities of AP

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value) reporting commercial name of analysed products, level, and typology of ageing of analysed materials, value of measured property.

The folder "Thermal and spectroscopic data on the characterization of mulch films.rar" available on [Zenodo](#) includes differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetry (TG), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and water contact angle (WCA) raw data and images relevant to the characterization of conventional and biodegradable mulch films. Seven mulching films consisting of 3 different conventional linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE, coded as PE) films and 4 different biodegradable (PBAT-based, coded as BIO) films are analysed. In particular, data regarding M-BIOIT-15-black-0, M-PEIT-15-black-0, M-BIOEL-15-black-0, M-PEEL-15-black-0, M-PEEL-50-transparent-0, M-BIODE-30-black-0 and M-BIOFI-15-black-0 are included.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

2.1. Data Summary

2.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information

2.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- experimental (e.g.
- gene sequencing data)
- Other

Primary data including experimental results from thermal and spectroscopic characterization.

2.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

The folder "Thermal and spectroscopic data on the characterization of mulch films.rar" includes differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetry (TG), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and water contact angle (WCA) raw data and images relevant to the characterization of conventional and biodegradable mulch films. 7 mulching films consisting of 3 different conventional linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE, coded as PE) films and 4 different biodegradable (PBAT-based, coded as BIO) films are analysed. In particular, data regarding M-BIOIT-15-black-0, M-PEIT-15-black-0, M-BIOEL-15-black-0, M-PEEL-15-black-0, M-PEEL-50-transparent-0, M-BIODE-30-black-0 and M-BIOFI-15-black-0 are included.

2.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

2.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

About 100 Mb

2.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

2.2. Reused Data

2.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

2.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Data Cite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

a. <https://opendefinition.org/>

license

b. <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

funders

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions.

<https://zenodo.org/records/10995989>

Mulch films consisting of three different conventional linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE, coded as M_PE) and four different biodegradable (PBAT-based, coded as M_BIO) films.

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Standard file formats for tabular data (.txt, .csv) and image data (.jpg). Some data will be uploaded as MS Excel format (.xlsx). However, they are included in a .rar folder, to be open with software suites including WinZip, WinRAR, etc.

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Standard file formats for tabular data (.txt, .csv) and image data (.jpg). Some data will be uploaded as MS Excel format (.xlsx).

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

No

Please describe if data require proprietary tools to access the data.

Data are included in a .rar folder, to be open with software suites including WinZip, WinRAR, etc.

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

2.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

<https://zenodo.org/records/10995989>

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/records/10995989>

Zenodo

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

Some files will require proprietary software to access, such as MS Office suite for .xls files.

Data are included in a .rar folder, to be open with software suites including WinZip, WinRAR, etc.

Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

No auxiliary data

2.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

2.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

Describe the data quality assurance processes.

Periodical calibration of the equipment, standardized procedure for sample preparation and analysis, replicated testing.

Will you provide any support for data reuse?

No

2.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

No

Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data.

Pierfrancesco Cerruti (orcid:0000-0003-0822-2866)

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

Zenodo

2.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time.

<https://zenodo.org/records/10995989>

2.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

2.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

3. SubTask 1.2.1. – Morphological and physical chemical characterization of main agricultural plastics articles used for protected cultivation systems during ageing in fields, and collection practices

Clusters of tabular data and images reporting level and typology of ageing of analysed materials, value of measured property. Estimated environmental losses during ageing.

The associated dataset available on Zenodo includes data generated upon the implementation of the ST 1.2.1 "Analysis of degradation and fragmentation of AP and transfer of MNP to soil". The activities dealt with the study of degradation and fragmentation from weathering and agricultural practices of conventional and biodegradable AP relevant for transfer of MNP to soil (during both use and end of life). In particular, the experimental data refer to characterization of biodegradable mulch films, pristine (coded M-BIO0) or subjected to photo-oxidative weathering (M-BIO192), as well as the same samples buried in soil for varying time periods, up to 353 days. The folders included contain gel permeation chromatography (GPC) and Matrix-assisted Laser Desorption Ionization (MALDI-TOF) data, which account for the change in film molecular weight upon soil burial. Furthermore, Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) data and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Water Contact Angle (WCA) images of some selected soil-buried samples are also provided.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

3.1. Data Summary

3.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

3.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- Sample or specimen data
- Other

3.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

3.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

3.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MG (megabyte)

Less than 100 Mb

3.1.6. To whom it might be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

3.2. Reused Data

3.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

a. <https://opendefinition.org/>

license

b. <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

funders

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions.

<https://zenodo.org/records/11195867>

Mulch films consisting of biodegradable, PBAT-based, polymer formulations, pristine (coded as M-BIO0) or subjected to photo-oxidative weathering for 192h (M-BIO192), as well as the same samples buried in soil for varying time periods, up to 353 days.

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

No

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/records/11195867>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Standard file formats for tabular data (.txt, .csv) and image data (.jpg, .tif). However, they are included in a .zip folder, to be opened with software suites including WinZip, WinRAR, etc.

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Standard file formats for tabular data (.txt, .csv) and image data (.jpg, .tif).

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

No

Data are included in a .rar folder, to be open with software suites including WinZip, WinRAR, etc.

Please describe if data require proprietary tools to access the data.

Data are included in a .rar folder, to be open with software suites including WinZip, WinRAR, etc.

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Zenodo

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/records/11195867>

Zenodo

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

No auxiliary data

3.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

Describe the data quality assurance processes

Periodical calibration of the equipment, standardized procedure for sample preparation and analysis, replicated testing.

Will you provide any support for data reuse?

No

3.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

No

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

Zenodo

3.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

<https://zenodo.org/records/11195867>

3.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

3.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

4. SubTask 1.2.2. – Quantitative and qualitative inventories of end-of life practices for AP

Task: End-of-life practices sourcing plastic pollution to soil

Tabular data (and metadata) listing of observed practices spatially referenced data of practices, quantitative assessment of plastic tonnages addressed to different practices, rank of practice as a potential source of plastic pollution.

This research involved the collection and thorough analysis of both virgin and used Agricultural Plastic (AP), alongside Agricultural Plastic Waste (APW) samples from Greece. The datasets provided include:

1. Quantitative and qualitative inventories of end-of-life practices for AP: This dataset comprises a table documenting the qualitative inventories of collected samples, as well as another table presenting mechanical testing results for quantitative analysis.
2. Images and audiovisual on end-of-life management practices: This dataset encompasses a series of photos illustrating virgin APs and collected APW.

Subtask 1.2.2: End-of-life Practices Sourcing Plastic Pollution to Soil

For this subtask, APW was gathered from both Greece and Italy. The dataset includes photos of the collected APW and highlights mismanagement practices leading to APW pollution.

3. Mismanagement and Collection of AP Residues from Regions Related to AP Waste (APW) Mismanagement, Potentially Contaminated by MNP - Greece.
4. Collection of AP Residues from Regions Related to AP Waste (APW) Mismanagement, Potentially Contaminated by MNP - Italy.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

4.1. Data Summary

4.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

4.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- observational (e.g.
- sensor data
- data from surveys)
- Other

4.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Multimedia
- Other

.xlsx and .jpg

4.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

4.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MG (megabyte)

4.1.6. To whom it might be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

4.2. Reused Data

4.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

4.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Data available on Zenodo

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Zenodo

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

a. <https://zenodo.org/records/11204123>

Zenodo

b. <https://zenodo.org/records/11186346>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

No

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

4.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

4.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

4.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

4.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

4.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

4.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

4.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

5. SubTask 1.2.2. – Images and audiovisual on end-of-life management practices.

Task: End-of-life practices sourcing plastic pollution to soil

Images and audio-visual documenting end of life practices (with metadata)

Images of Mismanagement and Collection of AP residues from regions related to AP Waste (APW) mismanagement, potentially contaminated by MNP-Greece

- <https://zenodo.org/records/11066395>

Images of Collection of AP residues from regions related to AP Waste (APW) mismanagement, potentially contaminated by MNP-Italy

- <https://zenodo.org/records/11066458>

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

5.1. Data Summary

5.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

5.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

5.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Multimedia

Images (.jpg)

5.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

5.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MG (megabyte)

5.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

5.2. Reused Data

5.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

5.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies.

a. <https://opendefinition.org/>

License

b. <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

Funders

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

Metadata is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine. immediately after publishing and sent to DataCite servers and indexed.

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

a. <https://zenodo.org/records/11066458>

Zenodo

b. <https://zenodo.org/records/11066395>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

5.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

At end of project

5.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

5.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

5.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

5.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time.

5.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

5.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

6. SubTask 1.2.3. – Quantitative (tabular data) and qualitative (text) description of Mulching film degradation in different case studies in Europe.

The dataset "Biodegradable mulching film degradation in soil in Italy" and the Image "Biodegradable mulching film degradation in soil in Italy" show the visible degradation process of biodegradable mulching samples in the soil at the experimental field of the University of Bari (Italy).

<https://zenodo.org/records/11048438>

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

6.1. Data Summary

6.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

6.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

6.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

6.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

6.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

6.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

6.2. Reused Data

6.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

6.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

6.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

6.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

6.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

6.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

6.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time.

6.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

6.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

7. SubTask 1.2.4. – Quantitative (tabular data) and qualitative (text) description of plastic chemical additives releases

Task: Release of AP chemical additives during ageing.

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value) reporting data of releases of selected chemical additives during ageing of agricultural plastics.

The folder "HPLC-ESI-MS data on the characterization of mulching film additives.rar" available on Zenodo includes liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry raw data (as .txt files) of the analyses of the additives carried out on two biodegradable mulch films (PBAT-based, coded as BIO). In particular, data regarding BIOIT-0 and BIOEL-0 refer to two pristine film samples, while those BIOIT-192 and BIOEL-192 are related to the same samples subjected to a 192-hour aging carried out by artificial solar light irradiation at 60 °C. Full scan and quantitative analysis runs are included. Furthermore, the experimental HPLC-ESI-MS runs carried out on varying concentration mixtures of standard compounds typically used as polymer additives has been included:

DioxyBenzone (cas:131-53-3; formula: C₁₄H₁₂O₄; MW:244,25 g/mol)

Triethyl O-Acetyl citrate (cas:77-89-4; formula: C₁₄H₂₂O₈; MW: 318,32 g/mol)

2-Hydroxy-4-(octyloxy) benzophenone (cas: 1843-05-6; formula: C₂₁H₂₆O₃; MW: 326,43 g/mol)

Octyl 3-Octyloxirane octanoic Acid (cas: 106-84-3; formula: C₂₆H₅₀O₃; MW: 410,67 g/mol)

Tris(2,4-tert-butylphenyl) phosphite (cas: 31570-04-4; formula: C₄₂H₆₃O₃P; MW: 646,92 g/mol)

cis-13-Docosenoamide (cas: 112-84-5; formula: C₂₂H₄₃NO; MW: 337,58 g/mol)

12-Hydroxystearic Acid (cas: 106-14-9; formula: C₁₈H₃₆O₃; MW: 300,48 g/mol)

2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-4-piperidinol (cas: 2403-88-5; formula: C₉H₁₉NO; MW: 157,25 g/mol)

2-(4,6-Diphenyl-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl)-5-[(hexyl)oxy]-phenol (cas: 147315-50-2; formula: C₂₇H₂₇N₃O₂; MW: 425,52 g/mol)

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

7.1. Data Summary

7.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

7.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- sample or specimen data
- Other

Primary HPLC-ESI-MS data on the characterization of mulching film additives.

7.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

.txt files in a .rar folder.

7.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

7.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

Size is less than 10 Mb.

7.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

7.2. Reused Data

7.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

7.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

all data are .txt format.

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <https://opendefinition.org/>

license

b. <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

funders

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

yes, the data folder is available on Zenodo

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/oai2d>

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/api/records/>

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

data are archived in a .rar folder.

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

all files are .txt file formats.

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

No

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

7.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

- Repository of Archive
- Other

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/11120715>

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

A software tool to open .rar files is required.

Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

No auxiliary data

7.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

7.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

Describe the data quality assurance processes

Periodical calibration of the equipment, standardized procedure for sample preparation and analysis, replicated testing.

Will you provide any support for data reuse?

No

7.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

No

Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

Sabrina Carola Carroccio (orcid:0000-0002-9645-0369)

Contact person

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

Zenodo

7.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time.

<https://zenodo.org/records/11120715>

7.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

7.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

8. SubTask 1.3.1. – Quantitative (tabular data) and qualitative (text) data of agricultural plastic uses in Europe

In order to analyse data concerning the agricultural plastic waste it is important to define the agricultural plastic used in Europe. Plastic is commonly used for: films for crop protection; nets; low tunnel films; soil mulching, solarization, and direct covering; bags and containers for pesticides, fertilizers, and other agrochemicals; silage bags; irrigation pipes; ropes and strings. Descriptions of different plastic application are given in the dataset "Agricultural plastic uses in Europe".

[Agricultural plastic waste in Italy-Greece-Spain-Portugal – Image](#)

[Agricultural plastic waste in Italy-Greece-Spain-Portugal – Dataset](#)

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

8.1. Data Summary

8.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

8.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Sample or specimen data

8.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files
- Other

.csv

8.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

8.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

KB (kilobyte)

8.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

8.2. Reused Data

8.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

8.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/oai2d>

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

No

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

.csv

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

8.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/records/11034413>

How will the data be made available?

Other

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records>

PAPILLONS Zenodo community

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

8.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

8.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

8.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

No

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

Zenodo

8.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time.

Zenodo

8.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

8.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

9. SubTask 1.3.2. – Quantitative (tabular data) and qualitative (text) data of agricultural plastic uses in Europe

The quantities of agricultural plastic waste across diverse agricultural applications (greenhouse covering films, mulching films, low tunnels films, nets, irrigation pipes, agrochemical containers, bags for fertilizers, and support equipment for vineyards) are mapped by means of GIS at the NUTS 2 regional level (EUROSTAT). The dataset Embargoed "Agricultural plastic waste in Italy-Greece-Spain-Portugal" is present in Zenodo. The data are embargoed because a paper is preparing.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

9.1. Data Summary

9.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

9.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

9.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

9.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

9.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

9.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

9.2. Reused Data

9.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

9.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

9.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

9.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

9.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

9.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

9.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time.

9.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

9.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

10. SubTask 1.4.1. – Catalogue of microplastic test materials

Task: Production of MNP reference materials

PDF files containing written descriptions and images of test materials, figures and tabular data detailing the particle size distribution and chemical characterisation for each batch of test materials.

This is currently being finalised as part of a submitted manuscript and will be uploaded to the PAPILLONS Zenodo community in May 2024.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

10.1. Data Summary

10.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

10.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

10.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

10.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

10.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

10.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

10.2. Reused Data

10.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

10.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

10.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

10.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

10.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

10.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

10.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

10.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

10.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

11. SubTask 1.4.2. – Protocols for analysis of MNPs and chemical additives in soil samples, water samples and biota samples.

Task: A Harmonisation and further development of methods for the analysis of MNP in soil, water, biota

Text files containing a written description of analytical procedures for microplastic isolation and analysis. These are currently under preparation for manuscripts describing method development work and are expected to be uploaded to the PAPILLONS Zenodo community by October 2024.

Text files containing tabular data related to the method development work undertaken for the determination of plastic additives from soil associated with the manuscript "Novel strategies for the determination of plastic additives derived from agricultural plastics in soil using ultrahigh-performance liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS)" under review in Science of the Total Environment. The dataset can be found on Zenodo, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10829115.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

11.1. Data Summary

11.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

11.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

11.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

11.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

11.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

11.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

11.2. Reused Data

11.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

11.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

11.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Other

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/10829115>)

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

11.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

11.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

11.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

11.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time.

<https://zenodo.org/records/10829115>

11.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

11.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

12. SubTask 1.4.3. – Protocols for spiking of test soils used in MNP behaviour and ecological effects studies

Task: MNP Standard reference soils for effects MNP behaviour and ecological effect studies

Text files with written descriptions of protocols used to spike test soils with PAPILLONS MNP test materials for the purpose of particle fate and ecological effects studies conducted in PAPILLONS. This includes tabular data and figures describing the quality check of spiking efficacy and consistency. Quality checking is currently under progress (microplastic analysis of spiked soil samples to check for variability in detected concentrations). This dataset is expected to be completed and uploaded to the Zenodo community at the end of the year 2024.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

12.1. Data Summary

12.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

12.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

12.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

12.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

12.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

12.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers

- Research communities
- Decision makers

12.2. Reused Data

12.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

12.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/>

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

12.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Other

<https://zenodo.org/>

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

12.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

12.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

12.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

12.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time.

12.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

12.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

13. Subask 2.2.1. – Micro and Nanoplastic contamination and distribution from field plot case studies

Task: Field plot experiments of MNP behaviour and transport

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description) reporting numbers and masses of micro and nanoplastics in European soils (including morphologic and chemical composition of particles)

- The dataset on “Plastic additive determination in soil collected from the field plot study” pertaining to sub-task “SubTask 2.2.1 - Micro and Nanoplastic contamination and distribution in soils from field plot case studies is currently completed in proportion of 50% percent covering the following elements:

- i) Pre-sampling samples from the German field plot
- ii) samples from Germany, Spain and Finland collected during 2022
- iii) samples from Spain collected during 2023

The expected delivery date of the corresponding datasets on PAPILLONS Zenodo Community is during 12/2024.

The samples were collected by our PAPILLONS partners. Quality assurance measures were in place during analysis including calibration curves, blank measurements and use of validated methods.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

13.1. Data Summary

13.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

13.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

13.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

13.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

13.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

13.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

13.2. Reused Data

13.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

13.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

As implemented by Zenodo

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/oai2d>

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

13.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Other

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

13.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

13.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

13.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

13.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

13.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

13.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

14. SubTask 2.2.2. – Micro and Nanoplastic contamination and distribution in soils from Climecs mesocosm experiments

Task: Controlled mesocosms studies of MNP behaviour and transport

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description) reporting numbers and masses of micro and nanoplastics in European soils (including morphological and chemical composition of particles

- The dataset on “Plastic additive determination in soil and lettuce collected within the frame of the mesocosm experiment” pertaining to sub-task “SubTask 2.2.2 - Micro and Nanoplastic contamination and distribution in soils from Climecs mesocosm experiments” is currently completed in proportion of 40% percent covering the following elements:

- i) Soil samples collected during the CLIMECS 2 study
- ii) Soil samples collected during the CLIMECS 3 study
- iii) Lettuce samples collected during the CLIMECS 3 study

The expected delivery date of the corresponding datasets on PAPILLONS Zenodo Community is during 12/2024.

The samples were collected by our partners in Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. Quality assurance measures were in place during analysis including calibration curves, blank measurements and use of validated methods.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

14.1. Data Summary

14.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

14.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

14.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

14.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

14.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

14.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

14.2. Reused Data

14.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

14.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/oai2d>

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

As implemented on <https://zenodo.org/>

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Other

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

14.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records>

Zenodo

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

14.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

14.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

14.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

14.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

14.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

14.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

15. SubTask 2.2.3. – Radiolabelled Micro and Nanoplastic distribution in soils from mesocosm studies

Task: Behaviour and transport of ¹⁴C-nanoplastics in a controlled environment

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description) reporting quantity of nanoplastics in different soil compartments of mesocosms (estimated through scintillation counting of radiolabelled materials).

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description) reporting quantity of nanoplastics in different components of crop plants (estimated through scintillation counting of radiolabelled materials).

This experiment is currently ongoing and as such the datasets are still being generated. The experiment is expected to finish during Summer 2024 and the datasets will be finalised and uploaded to the PAPILLONS community on Zenodo by the end of the year 2024.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

15.1. Data Summary

15.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

15.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

Uptake of ¹⁴C-labelled nanoplastics by crops.

15.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

15.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

15.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

15.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

15.2. Reused Data

15.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

15.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

15.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

15.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

15.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

15.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

15.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

15.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

15.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

16. SubTask 2.3.1. – Microplastic transport efficiency from runoff experiments

Task: Transfer and behaviour of MNP to groundwater and surface water

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description) reporting estimators of the transport efficiency of microplastics during runoff experiments

Dataset of microplastic mobilization rates in response to factors such as precipitation and crop development is under preparation. It pertains to task "2.3. MNP and additives transport to groundwater, surface water, air and uptake by biota and crop" and sub-task "Transfer and behaviour of MNP to groundwater and surface water". The runoff experiment at the modified pinson collector (IMDEA) experiment is currently completed in proportion of 60 percent, covering the following elements:

- Experimental development performed
- Soil and water sampling performed
- Sample treatment and analysis under development

Infiltration and surface runoff water samples together with soil samples at different depths were collected from modified Pinson collectors. Two experimental treatments (three replicates) were run. Film microplastics were added in all systems. Samples were collected during crop development and rainfall events. Bare soil was used as a control. Samples are being processed using FT-IR.

Data structure will include number of microplastics and their characterization in the samples collected to define the fate of such particles and their transport efficiency.

The dataset on "Plastic additive determination in run-off water" pertaining to sub-task "SubTask 2.3.1 - Microplastic transport efficiency from runoff experiments" is currently completed in proportion of 20% percent covering the following elements:

- i) LC-MS method optimization
- ii) Run-off water samples analysis

The samples were collected by our partners IMDEA. Quality assurance measures were in place during analysis including calibration curves, blank measurements and use of validated methods.

The expected delivery date of the corresponding datasets on PAPILLONS Zenodo Community is during 12/2024.

Task: Lateral Microplastic Transport

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels, and definitions of missing values, along with experimental design descriptions) reporting the transport (count) of microplastic particles during runoff experiments.

The dataset entails the transport of microplastics (MP) during heavy rainfall events, as a function of slope gradients (1°, 3°, 9°) and tillage practices, utilizing eight independent soil-filled containers (approximately 80 x 80 x 20 cm). The soil was spiked with field-relevant concentrations (about 7 g/m², 50 mg/kg dw) of polyvinyl terephthalate (PET), polystyrene (PS), and tire wear (TW). Runoff from each container is collected to assess MP transport. MPs are either distributed onto the soil surface to simulate worst-case scenarios (Experiment 1) or integrated into the soil to enhance field relevance (Experiment 2). Both experiments have been conducted, with Experiment 1 samples currently undergoing analysis (approximately 25% complete). Analysis of Experiment 2 samples will follow.

A third experiment is scheduled for late spring / early summer to investigate vegetation effects on lateral MP transport. Runoff will be collected, and MP particles analysed as in the previous experiments.

For each experiment, samples are assigned consecutive numbers to minimize reference to specific treatments, thus reducing systematic errors in analysis.

Datasets from all three experiments will be available to the PAPILLONS Zenodo community no later than December 2024.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

16.1. Data Summary

16.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

16.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- experimental (e.g.
- gene sequencing data)
- Other

Number of microplastics and their characterization together with additive concentrations in the samples collected from the runoff experiment

16.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files
- Numerical

16.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

16.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

16.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

16.2. Reused Data

16.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

16.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

As used by Zenodo

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/oai2d>

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/>

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

16.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records>

PAPILLONS Zenodo community

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

16.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

16.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

16.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

16.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

16.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

16.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

17. SubTask 2.3.2. – Microplastic atmospheric transport data in agricultural areas

Task: Atmospheric transport of AP

Clusters of tabular data on spatio-temporally resolved microplastic deposition fluxes in relation to meteorological variables (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description) reporting estimators of the air transport efficiency of microplastics.

Atmospheric deposition was collected monthly over a period of one year at three study sites in Spain, Germany and Finland. A total of 38 monthly field samples and 38 blank samples were taken and analysed for MP contamination.

The data is currently being analysed and will be made available to the PAPILLONS Zenodo community from 7/2024

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

17.1. Data Summary

17.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

17.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

17.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

17.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

17.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

17.1.6.To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

17.2. Reused Data

17.2.1.Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

17.2.2.Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/oai2d>

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/>

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

17.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records>

Zenodo PAPILLONS community

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

17.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

17.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

17.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

17.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

17.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

17.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

18. SubTask 4.1.1. – Ecotoxicology of MNPs on plant cells, seeds and emerging plants

Task: Ecotoxicology of MNPs on plant cells, seeds and emerging plants

Clusters of tabular data of plant cell responses, seed germination, plant growth and quality (several endpoints) (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description)

Publication and dataset

Zantis et al. 2023. Nano- and microplastics commonly cause adverse impacts on plants at environmentally relevant levels: A systematic review:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.161211>, <https://zenodo.org/records/10361822>

Adamczyk, S. (2023). Raw data for the publication: Polystyrene nanoparticles induce concerted response of plant defense mechanisms in plant cells, *Scientific Reports* (13): 22423. Suspension culture : <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-50104-5>, <https://zenodo.org/records/10853055>

Method paper: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiotec.2023.07.008>,
<https://zenodo.org/records/10210187>

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

18.1. Data Summary

18.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

18.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Sample or specimen data

Nano- and microplastics commonly cause adverse impacts on plants at environmentally relevant levels: A systematic review: a) Studies collected under a systematic literature search through two online publication databases (Web of Sciences and PubMed); b) trained personnel and validated methods; c) Studies were regrouped in three categories: 1) seed germination and early development, 2) Plant growth and 3) Biochemical biomarkers. Effects were recorded at the Lowest Observable Effect Concentrations (LOEC) for each observation.

Polystyrene nanoparticles induce concerted response of plant defence mechanisms in plant cells | Scientific Reports: Suspension culture: Treatment, timepoint and plant species information. Activity of glutathione ascorbate cycle and other biochemical indicators such as lipid peroxidation, production of secondary compounds, and stress hormones.

18.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Numerical

18.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Secondary data

18.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

KB (kilobyte)

Less than a megabyte

18.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

18.2. Reused Data

18.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

18.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

The data is described in detail in the publications that are openly available on Zenodo

Please provide URL/Location describing the used metadata schema

a. <https://zenodo.org/records/10361822>

Zenodo

b. <https://zenodo.org/records/10853055>

Zenodo

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Zenodo identifiers

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

Zenodo

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Metadata repository

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records>

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

No

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Excell files can be read by open office etc.

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

18.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records>

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

a. <https://zenodo.org/records/10361822>

Zenodo

b. <https://zenodo.org/records/10853055>

Zenodo

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

No auxiliary data

18.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

18.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

Will you provide any support for data reuse?

No

18.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

No

Data uploaded at publication of each article to Zenodo, no management after that required

Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a. Laura Zantis (orcid:0000-0002-8682-8727)

Corresponding author

b. Sylwia Adamczyk (orcid:0000-0002-9051-9302)

Corresponding author

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

Zenodo

18.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

Zenodo and Project TEAMS folder

18.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

18.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

19. SubTask 4.1.2. – Plant performance in MNP-Soil Plant system

Task: Plant performance in MNP-Soil-Plant system

[Species-dependent responses of crop plants to polystyrene microplastics](#)

[Contrasting the Impact of Biodegradable and Traditional Microplastics from Mulch on Crop Growth, Pot plant experiment](#)

Biodegradable microplastics induce profound changes in lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) defence mechanisms and to some extent deteriorate growth traits in mesocosm experiment. CLIMECS1: Treatment and timepoint information. Effects on basic traits tests such as biomass, growth, and biomass allocation (plant tissue ratio), Necrotic tissue and Specific leaf area. Stochiometric ratios (e.g. C: N), Dry weight percentage and Chlorophyll. Biochemical indicators such as DNA methylation, Lipid peroxidation, Production of secondary compounds, Generation of reactive oxygen species, Activity of glutathione ascorbate cycle, Abscisic and Salicylic acid stress hormones.

CLIMECS 3: Impacts of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on lettuce under realistic exposure conditions (in progress)

The impact of leachates from conventional and biodegradable plastic mulch films on plants and aquatic invertebrates

Uptake of ¹⁴C-labelled nanoplastics by crops.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

19.1. Data Summary

19.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

19.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- sample or specimen data
- experimental (e.g.
- gene sequencing data)

Species-dependent responses of crop plants to polystyrene microplastics: a) acute 7-14d test (lettuce, carrot, wheat and barley) and chronic hydroponic 21-d test (lettuce + wheat) conducted under laboratory conditions, b) trained personnel, validated methods, well equipped laboratories, internal standards when needed, c) For both the acute and chronic experiment we have plant, treatment and timepoint information. Acute effects on basic traits, including germination, shoot length, root length and biomass. Chronic effects on basic traits such as biomass, shoot- and root length, Necrotic tissue and Specific leaf area and Chlorophyll content. Biochemical indicators such as lipid peroxidation, total phenolic content, salicylic acid stress hormones.

Contrasting the Impact of Biodegradable and Traditional Microplastics from Mulch on Crop Growth: a) acute 7-14d test (lettuce, carrot, wheat and barley) and chronic hydroponic 21-d test (lettuce + barley) conducted under laboratory conditions, b) trained personnel, validated methods, well equipped laboratories, internal standards when needed, c) For both the acute and chronic experiment we have plant, treatment and timepoint information. Acute effects on basic traits, including germination, shoot length, root length and biomass. Chronic effects on basic traits such as biomass, shoot- and root length, Necrotic tissue and Specific leaf area and Chlorophyll content.

Biodegradable microplastics induce profound changes in lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) defence mechanisms and to some extent deteriorate growth traits in mesocosm experiment: a) lettuce samples collected during and in the end of the three-month experiment, b) trained personnel, validated methods, well equipped laboratories, internal standards when needed, c) CLIMECS1: Treatment and timepoint information. Effects on basic traits tests such as biomass, growth, and biomass allocation (plant tissue ratio), Necrotic tissue and Specific leaf area. Stochiometric ratios (e.g. C: N), Dry weight percentage and Chlorophyll. Biochemical indicators such as lipid peroxidation, Production of secondary compounds, Activity of glutathione ascorbate cycle, Salicylic acid stress hormones.

CLIMECS 3: Impacts of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on lettuce under realistic exposure conditions (in progress): a) lettuce samples collected during and in the end of the three-month experiment using PBAT-starch blend and PE in CLIMECS experimental setup at VU (Amsterdam), b) trained personnel, validated methods, well equipped laboratories, internal standards when needed, c) CLIMECS3: Treatment and timepoint information present. Effects on basic traits tests such as biomass, growth, and biomass allocation (plant tissue ratio), Necrotic tissue and Specific leaf area. Stochiometric ratios (e.g. C: N), Dry weight percentage and Chlorophyll. Biochemical indicators such as lipid peroxidation, Production of secondary compounds, Activity of glutathione ascorbate cycle, Salicylic acid stress hormones. Protein and sugar content

The impact of leachates from conventional and biodegradable plastic mulch films on plants and aquatic invertebrates: a) PLANTS: acute 7-14d test (lettuce, carrot, wheat and barley) and chronic hydroponic 21-d test (lettuce + wheat) conducted under laboratory conditions, AQUATIC INVERTS: *Daphnia magna* reproductive test and *C. Riparius* reproductive test according to OECD guidelines b) trained personnel, validated methods, well equipped laboratories, internal standards when needed, c) PLANTS: For both the acute and chronic experiment we have plant, treatment and timepoint information. Acute effects on basic traits, including germination, shoot length, root length and biomass. Chronic effects on basic traits such as biomass, shoot- and root length, Necrotic tissue and Specific leaf area and Chlorophyll content. Biochemical indicators such as lipid peroxidation, total phenolic content, salicylic acid stress

hormones. INVERTS: For both species we collect impact on reproduction, growth, population biomass and behaviour.

Uptake of ¹⁴C-labelled nanoplastics by crops.

19.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files
- Numerical

19.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

- Primary data
- Secondary data

19.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

KB (kilobyte)

less than a megabyte

19.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

19.2. Reused Data

19.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

19.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

No

Data described in detail in the publication

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Zenodo

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Zenodo

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

No

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

No

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

19.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records>

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records>

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

a. <https://zenodo.org/records/10361834>

Zenodo

b. <https://zenodo.org/records/10161131>

Zenodo

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

No auxiliary data

19.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

19.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records>

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

Will you provide any support for data reuse?

No

19.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

No

Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a. Laura Zantis (orcid:0000-0002-8682-8727)

Corresponding author

b. Sylwia Adamczyk (orcid:0000-0002-9051-9302)

Corresponding author

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

19.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

19.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

19.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

20. SubTask 4.1.3. – Relevance of environmental factors on MNP-induced effects on plant performance

Task: Relevance of environmental factors on MNP-induced effects on plant performance

Clusters of tabular data of plant growth and quality (several endpoints) (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description)

Field experiment: Impacts of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on barley under field conditions in three pedoclimatic regions (in progress)

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

20.1. Data Summary

20.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

20.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

Field experiment: Impacts of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on barley under field conditions in three pedoclimatic regions (in progress)

Datasets will be provided accordingly: a) barley samples collected during field experiments, b) trained personnel, validated methods, well equipped laboratories, internal standards when needed, c) Field experiments: Treatment and timepoint information. Effects on basic traits tests such as biomass, growth, and biomass allocation (plant tissue ratio), Necrotic tissue and Specific leaf area. Stoichiometric ratios (e.g. C: N), Dry weight percentage and Chlorophyll. Biochemical indicators such as lipid peroxidation, Production of secondary compounds, Activity of glutathione ascorbate cycle, Salicylic acid stress hormones.

20.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

20.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

20.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

20.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

20.2. Reused Data

20.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

20.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

20.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

20.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

20.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

20.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

20.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

20.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

20.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

21. Task 4.2. – Data and results of the socio-economic cost-benefit analysis from three European case studies

Task 4.2: Socio-economic sustainability of AP

Clusters of tabular data corresponding to the three socio-economic cost-benefit analysis carried out at farm level in three European case studies.

Datasets current status: As Task 4.2 started recently, we are in the preparatory phase of designing data collection, defining boundaries and limitations of the analysis, etc.

Expected delivery date: The expected delivery date of the corresponding datasets on PAPILLONS Zenodo Community is April 2025.

Datasets description: Costs and benefits will be identified as comprehensively as possible, and delineated in terms that are measurable, in terms of impacts on farm economics. Three European case studies will be selected considering the data provided by WP1 and the inputs from stakeholders (e.g. Agricultural Plastics Europe, farmer organisations) via a questionnaire-based survey and expert interviews (as needed in the different stages of the cost-benefit analysis).

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

21.1. Data Summary

21.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

21.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

Sample or specimen data, observational (data from survey), data elicited from experts, data from systematic literature review

21.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files
- Numerical

- Models

21.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

Primary and secondary data

21.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

21.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

21.2. Reused Data

21.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

21.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

21.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

after publication

21.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

21.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

21.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

Valentina Tartiu (orcid:0000-0002-7272-9824)

Contact person

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

21.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

21.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

Yes

Are the described data personal?

Yes

What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements

21.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

22. Task 5.2. – Data and Result analysis from stakeholder scoping

Task: Development and implementation of dissemination and exploitation plan (stakeholder scoping).

Text files and PowerPoint presentations

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

22.1. Data Summary

22.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

22.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

22.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

22.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

22.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

22.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

22.2. Reused Data

22.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

22.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

22.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

22.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

22.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

22.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

22.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

22.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

22.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

23. Task 2.1. – Micro and Nanoplastic contamination in European agricultural soils

Task: MNP source apportionment in European agricultural soils

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value) reporting numbers and masses of micro and nanoplastics in European soils (including morphological and chemical composition of particles) and numbers and polymer type of macroplastics.

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value) reporting plastic additive determination in soils collected within the frame of the European Spatial Survey. This dataset is currently completed in proportion of 70% percent covering the following elements:

i) Soil samples collected from Germany, Czech Republic, Italy, Spain, Greece, Norway & Finland

The expected delivery date of the corresponding datasets on PAPILLONS Zenodo Community is during 6/2024.

The samples were collected by our PAPILLONS partners. Quality assurance measures were in place during analysis including calibration curves, blank measurements and use of validated methods.

Clusters of tabular data with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value) reporting numbers and masses of microplastics in earthworms sampled in European soils (including morphological and chemical composition of particles). This dataset is currently being generated and is expected to be completed and delivered on the PAPILLONS Zenodo community during 7/2024

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

23.1. Data Summary

23.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

23.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

23.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

23.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

23.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

23.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

23.2. Reused Data

23.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

23.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/oai2d>

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

As implemented on Zenodo with rest api access and ui access

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

23.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records>

Zenodo PAPILLONS community

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

23.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

23.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

23.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

23.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

23.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

23.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

24. SubTask 2.3.1. – MNP transport through soils under variable saturation conditions

Task: Transfer and behaviour of MNP to groundwater and surface water

Clusters of tabular data (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description) reporting estimators of the transport efficiency of micro-nano-plastics during infiltration through soils and breakthrough curves in column experiments under variable saturation conditions.

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10887824>

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10932192>

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10931958>

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

24.1. Data Summary

24.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

24.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- experimental (e.g.
- gene sequencing data)
- Other

Concentrations of micro-nano-plastics from the column outlet in soil column experiments during time generating experimental breakthrough curves.

24.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

24.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

24.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

24.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

24.2. Reused Data

24.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

24.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/oai2d>

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/oai2d>

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

24.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Other

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

24.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

24.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

24.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

24.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

24.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

24.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

25. SubTask 1.3.1. – Datasets concerning plastic waste indices

Agricultural activities have been positively affected using plastic products, but this has resulted in the production of plastic waste and led to an increase in environmental pollution. Two datasets are in ZENODO concerning plastic waste indices to different crop types and plastic products allowed quantifying and georeferencing actual plastic waste production.

<https://zenodo.org/records/10928002>

<https://zenodo.org/records/10927676>

<https://zenodo.org/records/10927881>

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

25.1. Data Summary

25.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To share information

25.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- observational (e.g.
- sensor data
- data from surveys)
- Other

25.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Numerical

25.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

25.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

KB (kilobyte)

25.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

25.2. Reused Data

25.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

25.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

Metadata available at Zenodo

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org>

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

25.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

The data are openly accessible at Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/10928002>

<https://zenodo.org/records/10927676>

<https://zenodo.org/records/10927881>

How will the data be made available?

Other

<https://zenodo.org>

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

25.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

25.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

25.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

25.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

25.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

25.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

26. SubTask 3.2.1. – Changes in microbial community composition and activity after exposure to microplastics in field plot and mesocosm experiments

Clusters of tabular data of values of molecular markers reflecting microbial community composition and organic matter degradation rates and properties (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description). These clusters of data are:

1. PAPILLONS CLIMECS1: Effects of biodegradable MNPs on soil microbial communities and microbial activity.

DOI and link in Zenodo: Sequence data will be uploaded in NCBI, other data in Zenodo: 10.5281/zenodo.10715716

Dataset current status: Dataset " PAPILLONS CLIMECS1: Effects of biodegradable MNPs on soil microbial communities and microbial activity" pertaining to sub-task 3.2.1 on soil microbes is currently completed in proportion of 90 percent, covering the soil microbial (bacterial and fungal) community analysis in PAPILLONS mesocosm experiment

Expected delivery date: The expected delivery date of the corresponding dataset on PAPILLONS Zenodo Community and NCBI is May 2024.

Detailed dataset description: Data is collected from PAPILLONS mesocosm experiment (first round). The bacterial V4-V5 region of the 16S rRNA gene was amplified using primers 515F-926R, and the fungal ITS genomic region was amplified using the ITS7 and the ITS4 primers. After the purification, the amplicon library was sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq platform. The bacterial taxonomy of each amplicon sequence variant (ASV) was assigned using the database. The alpha diversity indices and relative abundances of bacterial and fungal communities were analysed, and the beta diversity was visualized using Bray-Curtis distances.

2. PAPILLONS CLIMECS3: Effects of conventional MNPs on soil microbial communities and microbial activity in CLIMECS mesocosms

DOI and link in Zenodo: Sequence data will be uploaded in NCBI, other data in Zenodo: 10.5281/zenodo.10715716

Dataset current status: Dataset "PAPILLONS CLIMECS3: Effects of biodegradable MNPs on soil microbial communities and microbial activity" pertaining to sub-task 3.2.1 on microbes is currently completed in proportion of 70 percent, covering the soil microbial (bacterial and fungal) community analysis in PAPILLONS mesocosm experiment

Expected delivery date: The expected delivery date of the corresponding dataset on PAPILLONS Zenodo Community and NCBI is in June 2024.

Detailed dataset description: Data is collected from PAPILLONS mesocosm experiment (third round). The bacterial V4-V5 region of the 16S rRNA gene was amplified using primers 515F-926R, and the fungal ITS genomic region was amplified using the ITS7 and the ITS4 primers. After the purification, the amplicon library was sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq platform. The bacterial taxonomy of each amplicon sequence variant (ASV) was assigned using the database. The alpha diversity indices and relative abundances of bacterial and fungal communities were analyzed, and the beta diversity was visualized using Bray-Curtis distances.

3. PAPILLONS Field experiment: Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on soil properties and processes

Dataset current status: Field experiment: Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on soil properties and processes” pertaining to task 3.2, on microbial functioning, is currently completed in proportion of 80%, covering the measurements of microbial activity, degradation of litter, measured by teabag approach and production of greenhouse gases (GHG; only in Finland).

Expected delivery date: December 2024

Detailed dataset description: Samples for microbial activity measurements were taken from the experimental fields at two sampling occasions after the growth season and harvest, in 2022 and 2023. The degradation of litter was followed during the growth seasons by placing teabags (green tea and rooibos tea) in soil and by measuring the mass loss of the tea after taken from the soil before harvest. Greenhouse gases released from soil were measured in Finland in 2023 by taking samples regularly. data collection methods and tools. Data includes raw data on microbial activity, GHG and tea biomass.

4. PAPILLONS Field experiment: Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on soil microbial community.

DOI and link in Zenodo:

Sequence data will be uploaded in NCBI, other data in Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.10715716](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10715716)

Dataset current status: Dataset " PAPILLONS Field experiment: Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on soil microbial community” pertaining to task 3.2.1 on soil microbial community is currently completed in proportion of 60 percent, covering the soil microbial (bacterial and fungal) community analysis in PAPILLONS field experiment.

Expected delivery date: The expected delivery date of the corresponding dataset on PAPILLONS Zenodo Community and NCBI is June 2024.

Detailed dataset description: Data is collected from the three field experiment sites located in Finland, Spain and Germany after growing seasons 2022 and 2023. The bacterial V4-V5 region of the 16S rRNA gene was amplified using primers 515F-926R, and the fungal ITS genomic region was amplified using the ITS7 and the ITS4 primers. After the purification, the amplicon library was sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq platform. The bacterial taxonomy of each amplicon sequence variant (ASV) was assigned using the database. The alpha diversity indices and relative abundances of bacterial and fungal communities were analysed, and the beta diversity was visualized using Bray-Curtis distances.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

26.1. Data Summary

26.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

26.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- experimental (e.g.
- gene sequencing data)
- Other

26.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

26.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

26.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

26.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

26.2. Reused Data

26.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

26.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <https://opendefinition.org/>

license

b. <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

funders

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

Metadata is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and sent to Datacite servers and indexed

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/records/10715716>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

26.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

26.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

26.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

26.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Other

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

26.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

26.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

26.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

27. SubTask 3.2.2. – Variability in microbial community composition in soils with varying microplastic concentrations

SubTask 3.2.2

Spatial surveys on covariance between microbial diversity and MNP distribution

Datasets name:

Variability in microbial community composition in soils with varying microplastic concentrations

Dataset description:

Tabular data of values of molecular markers reflecting microbial community composition (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description).

Data is collected from the 39 soil samples of spatial surveys in European regions (Germany, Spain, Finland and Czech Republic). Each soil sample was treated with conventional and biodegradable microplastics (two different concentrations), and each soil was incubated in the laboratorial conditions. The bacterial V4-V5 region of the 16S rRNA gene was amplified using primers 515F-926R, and the fungal ITS genomic region was amplified using the fITS7 and the ITS4 primers. After the purification, the amplicon library was sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq platform. The bacterial taxonomy of each amplicon sequence variant (ASV) was assigned using the database. The alpha diversity indices and relative abundances of bacterial and fungal communities were analysed, and the beta diversity was visualized using Bray-Curtis distances.

1. PAPILLONS European Spatial Survey: Microbial community in relation to microplastic load in European field soils

DOI and link in Zenodo:

Sequence data will be uploaded in NCBI, other data in Zenodo

Dataset current status:

The dataset is currently completed in proportion of 60 percent.

The expected delivery date of the corresponding dataset on PAPILLONS Zenodo Community and NCBI is June 2024.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

27.1. Data Summary

27.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

27.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

27.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

27.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

27.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

27.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

27.2. Reused Data

27.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

27.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <https://opendefinition.org/>

license

b. <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

funders

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

Metadata is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and sent to DataCite servers and indexed

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

27.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

27.2.4. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

27.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Other

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

27.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

27.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

27.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

28. SubTask 3.3.1. – Ecotoxicological responses of soil invertebrates after exposure to microplastic in single species test

Clusters of tabular data on the impacts of microplastics on soil invertebrates (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description). These clusters of data are:

- Effects of microplastics on Enchytraeid multigeneration reproduction and soil physicochemical properties

DOI and link in Zenodo: [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11058373](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11058373)

- Survival and reproduction effects of microplastics from three agricultural mulching films on *Folsomia candida*, *Sinella curviseta*, *Heteromurus nitidus* and *Ceratophysella denticulate* (Collembola)

DOI and link in Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11031991>

- Multigenerational toxicity of microplastics derived from two types of agricultural mulching films to *Folsomia candida*

DOI and link in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/11032128>

- Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on the earthworm *Eisenia andrei* in two generations

Link in Zenodo: [Raw data for the submitted manuscript entitled "Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on earthworm *Eisenia andrei* in two generations" \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org/records/11032128)

Dataset current status: Dataset " Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on the earthworm *Eisenia andrei* in two generations pertaining to task/ sub-task 3.3.1 is currently completed in proportion of 95 percent, covering the data on earthworm growth, reproduction, energy reserves and energy transfer system.

Expected delivery date: September 2024

Detailed dataset description: Earthworm *Eisenia andrei* to microplastics made of recycled PE and PBAT mulching film materials (PE-MP and PBAT-BD-MP) in long-term 7-month laboratory experiment in concentrations of 0%, 0.005%, 0.05%, 0.1%, 0.5%, 1% and 5%. The growth, reproduction, total energy reserves and electron transport system (ETS) activity in *E. andrei* in two generations were measured. The data includes raw data on the biomass of the earthworms in the first generation and second generation, number of produced juveniles in the first and second generation and the biomarker data on the first and second generation.

- Reproduction, growth and oxidative stress in the earthworm *Eisenia andrei* exposed to conventional and biodegradable mulching film microplastic

DOI and link in Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.11072799](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11072799)

- Raw data for the submitted manuscript: Response of the terrestrial crustacean *Porcellio scaber* and the mealworm *Tenebrio molitor* to agricultural microplastics exposure: comparison of nondegradable and biodegradable fossil-based mulching films

DOI and link in Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.11004318](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11004318)

- Raw data for the submitted manuscript Multigenerational effects of agricultural microplastics on the mealworm *Tenebrio molitor*

DOI and link in Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.11004411](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11004411)

- Effect of microplastic from two agricultural mulch films in soil on the colony founding ability of ant queens

Dataset on MNP effects on ant colony founding pertaining to sub-task 3.3.1 is currently completed in proportion of 70 percent, covering the following elements: tabular data sets on ant queen survival, colony size (number of eggs, larvae, pupae, workers) and biological markers in the early colony establishment phase in response to soil contamination with MNP from LDPE and starch-based PBAT at MNP-soil concentrations of 0%, 0.05%, 0.5% and 5%. The test MNP concentrations represent environmentally relevant, highly contaminated, and worst-case scenarios.

Observational data on ant queen survival and colony size was collected weekly during the test period of four months. All aspects of quality control have been considered to ensure that the tests and data provided meet quality standards. Attention was paid to a high number of repetitions, the use of plastic-free tools and containers to avoid additional contamination, even mixing of test MNP with soil, controlled conditions in the climate chamber and control tests.

The data set is expected to be available in the PAPILLONS Zenodo Community in the course of 08.2024.

- Effect of microplastics as a food additive on the survival and size of ant colonies

Dataset on effects of MNP as food additive on ant colony size and growth pertaining to sub-task 3.3.1 is currently completed in proportion of 30 percent, covering the following elements: tabular data sets on ant queen survival, colony size (number of eggs, larvae, pupae, workers) and biological markers in response to food contamination with MNP from LDPE and starch-based PBAT at MNP concentrations of 0%, 0.05% and 0.5%.

Observational data on ant queen survival and colony size was collected at the end of the test. All aspects of quality control have been considered to ensure that the tests and data provided meet quality standards. Attention was paid to a high number of repetitions, the use of plastic-free tools and containers to avoid additional contamination, even mixing of test MNP with food, controlled conditions in the climate chamber and control tests.

The data set is expected to be available in the PAPILLONS Zenodo Community in the course of 08.2024.

- Effects of long-term exposure to soil contamination with microplastics on *Lasius niger* ant colonies

Dataset on effects of long-term exposure to MNP in soil on the growth and size of ant colonies pertaining to sub-task 3.3.1 is currently completed in proportion of 0 percent. The test is still ongoing and will end in July 2024. The datasets will cover the following elements:

tabular data sets on ant queen survival, colony size (number of eggs, larvae, pupae, workers) and biological markers in response to soil contamination with MNP from LDPE and starch-based PBAT at MNP-soil concentrations of 0%, 0.5%. The test MNP concentrations represent highly contaminated soil.

Observational data on ant queen survival and colony size will be collected at the end of the test. All aspects of quality control have been considered to ensure that the tests and data provided meet quality standards. Attention was paid to a high number of repetitions, the use of plastic-free tools and containers to avoid additional contamination, even mixing of test MNP with soil, controlled conditions in the climate chamber and control tests.

The data set is expected to be available in the PAPILLONS Zenodo Community in the course of 11.2024.

- Trophic transfer of microplastics from contaminated soils via worms to beetles

Dataset on trophic transfer of MNP from soil via worm to beetles pertaining to sub-task 3.3.1 is currently completed in proportion of 0 percent. The test is currently in the preparatory phase and will begin in June 2024. The datasets will cover the following elements: tabular data sets on beetle survival and MP trophic level transfer efficiency. MNP from LDPE and starch-based PBAT at MNP-soil concentrations of 0%, 0.05%, and 0.5% will be tested.

Observational data on beetle survival and trophic level transfer efficiency will be collected at the end of the test. All aspects of quality control have been considered to ensure that the tests and data provided meet quality standards. Attention was paid to a high number of repetitions, the use of plastic-free tools and containers to avoid additional contamination, even mixing of test MNP with soil, controlled conditions in the climate chamber and control tests.

The data set is expected to be available in the PAPILLONS Zenodo Community in the course of 11.2024.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

28.1. Data Summary

28.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

28.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

28.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

28.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

28.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

28.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

28.2. Reused Data

28.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

28.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <https://opendefinition.org/>

license

b. <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

funders

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

Metadata is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and sent to DataCite servers and indexed

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

No

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

28.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Zenodo

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

a. <https://zenodo.org/records/11058374>

Zenodo

b. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11031991>

Zenodo

c. <https://zenodo.org/records/11032128>

Zenodo

d. <https://zenodo.org/records/10990380>

Zenodo

e. <https://zenodo.org/records/11072799>

Zenodo

f. <https://zenodo.org/records/11004318> / <https://zenodo.org/records/11004411>

Zenodo

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

28.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

28.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

28.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Other

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

28.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

28.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

28.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

29. SubTask 3.3.2. – Changes in soil invertebrate communities and properties during mesocosm experiments with added microplastics

Clusters of tabular data of community composition and population characteristics in mesocosm experiments with added microplastics (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description). These clusters of data are:

- **PAPILLONS CLIMECS1: Effect of biodegradable MNPs on soil invertebrates and physicochemical properties in CLIMECS mesocosms**

Dataset current status: The dataset “Effect of MNPs on soil invertebrates and physicochemical properties in CLIMECS mesocosm” pertaining to task 3.3 on soil invertebrates is currently completed in proportion of 80 percent, covering the following elements on soil invertebrates: Earthworm survival, weight and reproduction and springtail community composition

Expected delivery date: December 2024

Detailed dataset description: Two earthworm species and three springtail species were added to the soil columns. Eight replicate soil columns per treatment (4 concentrations of PBAT MNPs) and controls. Earthworms recovered were identified to species, counted and weighted. Springtails were extracted, counted and identified to species. All species were identified using established taxonomic keys, all analyses followed accepted standardized methods. The invertebrate data includes the lists of earthworm and springtail numbers and species and earthworm masses.

- **PAPILLONS CLIMECS3: Effects of conventional MNPs on soil biota and physicochemical properties in CLIMECS mesocosms**

Dataset current status: The dataset “Effect of MNPs on soil invertebrates and physicochemical properties in CLIMECS mesocosm” pertaining to task 3.3 on soil invertebrates is currently completed in proportion of 50 percent, covering the following elements on soil invertebrates: Earthworm survival and reproduction, springtail community composition.

Expected delivery date: February 2025

Detailed dataset description: Two earthworm species and three springtail species were added to the soil columns. Eight replicate soil columns per treatment (3 concentrations of LLDPE MNPs, 1 concentration of PBAT and controls). Earthworms recovered were identified to species and counted. Springtails were extracted, counted and identified to species. All species were identified using established taxonomic keys, all analyses followed accepted standardized methods. The data on invertebrates includes the lists of earthworm and springtail numbers and species.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

29.1. Data Summary

29.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

29.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

29.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

29.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

29.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

29.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

29.2. Reused Data

29.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

29.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <https://opendefinition.org/>

license

b. <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

funders

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

Metadata is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and sent to Datacite servers and indexed.

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

29.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

29.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

29.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

29.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Other

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

29.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

29.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

29.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

30. SubTask 3.3.3. – Soil invertebrate communities in experimental fields and European agricultural fields with varying loads of microplastics

Clusters of tabular data of community composition and population characteristics (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description) in field plot experiment with added microplastics. These clusters of data are:

- **PAPILLONS Field-plot experiment: Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on soil invertebrates**

Dataset current status: The dataset “Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on soil invertebrates” pertaining to sub-task “3.3.3” is currently completed in proportion of 40 percent, covering the earthworm, enchytraeid, springtail and mite abundances and species diversity as well as microfauna species diversity assessed by eDNA methods. The data on earthworms and enchytraeids have been counted, the data on springtails and mites will be available by December 2024. The eDNA samples have been extracted and currently are sequenced, but still need data analysis.

Expected delivery date: January 2025

Detailed dataset description: Earthworms were collected from the different field plots by excavating 25 x 25 cm soil samples and searching for earthworms by hand sorting. Deeper living worms were expelled from the soil by adding a mustard solution into the hole. All collected worms were stored in ethanol for analysis. Enchytraeids were sampled from the three experimental fields in Spain, Germany and Finland by taking three soil samples from each plot using soil auger with diameter of 5.5 cm. The enchytraeids were extracted from soil samples using wet funnels, after which the number and length of the enchytraeid worms were measured under microscope. Also, microarthropods were sampled by taking three soil samples per plot in each experimental field, after which they were extracted from the soil samples using Tullgren or High gradient extraction. Soil samples were taken and extracted also for DNA, which will be sequenced using selected primers to identify soil microfauna. Species identification used established taxonomic keys for earthworms and springtails; enchytraeid and mites were only counted distinguishing major taxonomic groups, eDNA data were analysed using selected primers. The data lists the numbers of animals and species for the different treatments within an experimental field, and for the two different years of sampling (2022, 2023).

- **PAPILLONS European Spatial Survey: Soil earthworm abundances in relation to MNP load in European agricultural soils**

Dataset current status: The dataset “Soil earthworm abundances in relation to MNP load in European agricultural soils” pertaining to sub-task 3.3.3 is currently completed in proportion of 80 percent, covering numbers of earthworms (adults, juveniles) and species identity collected from different field sites sampled within the PAPILLONS European Spatial Survey. Earthworm abundance data and community composition still have to be related to agricultural practices, and measurements on microplastic concentrations and other soil parameters.

Expected delivery date: July 2024

Detailed dataset description: Earthworms were collected from the different field plots by excavating 25 x 25 cm soil samples and searching for earthworms by hand sorting. Deeper living worms were expelled from the soil by adding a mustard solution into the hole. All collected worms were stored in ethanol for analysis. Adult earthworms were identified down to species using taxonomic keys, juveniles were just counted. The data consist of lists of earthworms per species and sample, and summed data for each sampled field.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

30.1. Data Summary

30.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

30.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

30.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

30.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

30.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

30.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

30.2. Reused Data

30.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

30.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <https://opendefinition.org/>

license

b. <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

funders

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

Metadata is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo' s search engine immediately after publishing and sent to DataCite servers and indexed

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

30.2.3.Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

30.2.4.Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

30.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

30.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Other

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

30.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept in secure, managed storage for limited time

30.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

30.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

31. SubTask 2.3.3. – Uptake of MNP by biota and crops

Dataset of uptake of microplastic by earthworms. Tabular data reporting microplastic counts (and a description of particle size and polymer type) isolated from earthworms included in a multi-generational single species test. This dataset is associated with a manuscript currently under preparation for Environmental Pollution. The dataset will be uploaded to Zenodo in June 2024 after revisions and final checks.

Dataset for "Quantitative tracking of nanoplastics along the food chain from lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) to snails (*Cantareus aspersus*)". The dataset contains the uptake of nanoplastics of different sizes in lettuce and translocation from roots to shoots, as well as trophic transfer to snails. Effects measured in plants include root and shoot biomass; SNAILS: Uptake in digestive gland and feces. Effects measured in growth parameters and behaviour. The dataset will be uploaded in Zenodo latest May 2024 as it is still going through a final check.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

31.1. Data Summary

31.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

31.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

31.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

31.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

31.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

31.1.6.To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

31.2. Reused Data

31.2.1.Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

31.2.2.Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <https://opendefinition.org/>

license

b. <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

funders

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

Metadata is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and sent to DataCite servers and indexed

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

31.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Please provide URL/Name of used data repositories

<https://zenodo.org/communities/papillons/records>

Zenodo PAPILLONS community

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

31.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

31.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

31.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Other

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

31.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

31.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

31.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

32. Task 3.1. – Changes in soil physicochemical properties by microplastics

Clusters of tabular data of values of selected soil physical-chemical properties (with metadata including variable labels, code labels and definition of missing value, experimental design description). These clusters of data are:

- **PAPILLONS laboratory experiment: Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on soil water retention characteristics**

DOI and link in Zenodo: 10.5281/zenodo.10965496

Dataset current status: dataset “Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on soil water retention characteristics” pertaining to task 3.1 is currently completed in proportion of 85%, covering volumetric water contents of control soils and soils amended with conventional or biodegradable microplastics (two concentrations and four replicates) with in suction pressures of 0.1, 0.3, 6.3, 10, 20, 32, 100, 320, 1600 and 39,000 kPa, and common water retention parameters.

Expected delivery date: The expected delivery date of the corresponding dataset on PAPILLONS Zenodo Community is May 2024.

Detailed dataset description: Data was collected in a water retention curve determination done for the laboratory-packed cylinders using sieved and homogenized soils collected from PAPILLONS field experiment sites and LUFA soil amended with conventional or biodegradable microplastics in two concentrations. In-house reference soil samples were included in the determinations, and they were packed in the cylinders in the same manner as the non-amended samples. Data includes characteristics of the four studied soils (LUFA, FI, SP, GE), volumetric water contents of control soils and soils amended with conventional or biodegradable microplastics (two concentrations and four replicates) with in suction pressures of 0.1, 0.3, 6.3, 10, 20, 32, 100, 320, 1600 and 39,000 kPa, and common water retention parameters organized in an excel file.

- **PAPILLONS CLIMECS1: Effect of MNPs on soil invertebrates and physicochemical properties in CLIMECS mesocosm**

DOI and link in Zenodo: Soil aggregations (raw data): <https://zenodo.org/uploads/11068076>

Dataset current status: The dataset “Effect of MNPs on soil invertebrates and physicochemical properties in CLIMECS mesocosm” soil properties pertaining to task 3.1 on soil properties is currently completed in proportion of “80” percent, covering the following elements on soil properties: soil pH, soil aggregation and microplastic concentration and particle size distributions

Expected delivery date: December 2024

Detailed dataset description: Two earthworm species and three springtail species were added to the soil columns. Eight replicate soil columns per treatment (4 concentrations of PBAT MNPs) and controls. Earthworms recovered were identified to species, counted and weighted. Springtails were extracted, counted and identified to species. Representative soil samples were taken for analysis of MNPs, soil

pH and aggregation. Data on soil properties includes lists of soil pH and soil aggregate distributions, per sample and treatment.

- **PAPILLONS CLIMECS3: Effects of conventional MNPs on soil biota and physicochemical properties in CLIMECS mesocosms**

Dataset current status: The dataset “Effect of MNPs on soil invertebrates and physicochemical properties in CLIMECS mesocosm” pertaining to task 3.1 on soil properties is currently completed in proportion of “50” percent, covering the following elements on soil properties: soil pH, soil penetrability, soil aggregation

Expected delivery date: February 2025

Detailed dataset description: Two earthworm species and three springtail species were added to the soil columns. Eight replicate soil columns per treatment (3 concentrations of LLDPE MNPs, 1 concentration of PBAT) and controls. Earthworms recovered were identified to species and counted. Springtails were extracted, counted and identified to species, Representative soil samples were taken for analysis of MNPs, soil pH and aggregation, soil penetrability was measured before collecting soil samples. All species were identified using established taxonomic keys, all analyses followed accepted standardized methods. Data includes lists of earthworm and springtail numbers and species, lists of pH values, lists of soil aggregate distributions, lists of soil penetration force, per sample and treatment.

- **PAPILLONS Field experiment: Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on soil properties and processes**

DOI and link in Zenodo: Soil aggregations (raw data); <https://zenodo.org/uploads/11068076>

Dataset current status: Dataset “Field experiment: Effects of conventional and biodegradable microplastics on soil properties and processes” pertaining to task 3.1 on soil properties is currently completed in proportion of 50%, covering the soil characteristics in three PAPILLONS field experiment sites and soil properties data after the first growing season (2022).

Expected delivery date: December 2024.

Detailed dataset description: Data is collected from the three field experiment sites located in Finland, Spain and Germany and include basic soil characteristics at the beginning of the experiment, and properties measured after growing seasons 2022 and 2023. Soil sampling and data collection has been done according to PAPILLONS’ “Protocol for field plot experiments in Finland, Germany and Spain. Data collected from the three field experiment sites located in Finland, Spain and Germany includes soil texture and chemical characteristics at the beginning of the experiment, and bulk density measured for undisturbed soil cores, pH and electric conductivity, water-extractable TOC/DOC, TDN, NH₄-N, NO₃-N and PO₄-P, measured after growing seasons 2022 and 2023 organized in an excel file.

Template: Horizon 2020

Type: Dataset

32.1. Data Summary

32.1.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

To obtain information

32.1.2. What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

Other

32.1.3. What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Text files

32.1.4. What is the origin of the described data?

Other

32.1.5. What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

32.1.6. To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

32.2. Reused Data

32.2.1. Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

32.2.2. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <https://opendefinition.org/>

license

b. <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

funders

Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

Persistent identifiers

DOI

Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

Metadata is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and sent to DataCite servers and indexed

What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Registry/Catalogue

Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

a. <https://zenodo.org/uploads/11068076>

Zenodo

b. <https://zenodo.org/uploads/10965496>

Zenodo

Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

No

Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

32.2.3. Making data openly accessible

Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

How will the data be made available?

Repository of Archive

Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

Secure with backup and recovery

Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

32.2.4. Making data interoperable

Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

32.2.5. Increase data reuse

When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

After article publication

Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

32.3. Allocation of resources

How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Other

Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not, who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Data Center Archive Storage

32.4. Data Security

Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

32.5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

Are the described data sensitive?

No

Are the described data personal?

No

32.6. Other

Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No